

Electronic Supplementary “Raw data”

Title: A mechanistic account of visual discomfort

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Architecture 1: raw data

Figure 1. **Discomfort rating** against **full model activation** in set **Architecture 1** for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=10). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 7, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the activation of the model response for each image (N = 74). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 2. **Discomfort rating** against **full model sparseness** in set **Architecture 1** for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=10). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 7, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the sparseness of the model response for each image (N = 74). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 3. **Discomfort rating** against full **model isotropy** in set **Architecture 1** for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=10). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 7, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the isotropy of the model response for each image (N = 74). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Architecture 2: raw data

Figure 4. **Discomfort rating** against full **model activation** in set **Architecture 2** for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=10). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 7, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the activation of the model response for each image (N = 74). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 5. **Discomfort rating** against full **model sparseness** in set **Architecture 2** for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=10). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 7, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the sparseness of the model response for each image (N = 74). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 6. **Discomfort rating** against full **model isotropy** in set **Architecture 2** for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=10). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 7, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the isotropy of the model response for each image (N = 74). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Art 1: raw data

Figure 7 (part 1). Discomfort rating against full model activation in set Art 1 for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=53). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 5, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the activation of the model response for each image (N = 50). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 7 (part 2). Continued from part 1.

Figure 8 (part 1). **Discomfort rating against full model sparseness** in set **Art 1** for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=53). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 5, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the sparseness of the model response for each image (N = 50). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 8 (part 2). Continued from part 1.

Figure 9 (part 1). **Discomfort rating against full model isotropy** in set **Art 1** for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=53). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 5, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the isotropy of the model response for each image (N = 50). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 9 (part 2). Continued from part 1.

Art 2: raw data

Figure 10 (part 1). **Discomfort rating** against **full model activation** in set **Art 2** for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=79). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 5, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the activation of the model response for each image (N = 50). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 10 (part 2). Continued from part 1.

Figure 10 (part 3). Continued from part 2.

Figure 11 (part 1). **Discomfort rating against full model sparseness** in set **Art 2** for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=79). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 5, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the sparseness of the model response for each image (N = 50). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 11 (part 2). Continued from part 1.

Figure 11 (part 3). Continued from part 2.

Figure 12 (part 1). **Discomfort rating against full model isotropy** in set **Art 2** for all the subjects included in the analysis (N=79). Panel numbers indicate subject identity. Each panel displays a subject's ratings (between 1 and 5, in order of increasing discomfort, see Methods) against the isotropy of the model response for each image (N = 50). Blue lines show best linear fit and shaded area shows 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 12 (part 2). Continued from part 1.

Figure 12 (part 3). Continued from part 2.